

Syntheses of Indophenazines and 6-Piperidino/morpholinomethylindophenazines as Possible Excystment and Cysticidal Agents*

RAJENDRA S. VARMA and IFTIKHAR A. KHAN

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 14 April 1978 ; accepted 21 July 1978

Isatin(s) were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamines to yield indophenazines(I). Indophenazines were then subjected to Mannich reaction conditions to furnish *o*-piperidinomethylindophenazines(II) and 6-morpholinomethylindophenazines(III). The compounds thus synthesised were evaluated for their ability to cause excystment and cysticidal activity against *Schizopyrenus russelli*.

ISATINS have generally been associated with antiviral activity¹. Some isatin derivatives have also been found to exhibit antibacterial², anthelmintic³ and hypotensive⁴ activity. Recently a series of 3-arylimino-2-indolinones and their N-methyl and N-piperidino/morpholinomethyl analogs were synthesised and evaluated as cysticidal and excystment agents⁵⁻⁷. The structural similarity between 3-arylimino-2-indolinones and indophenazines(I) led the authors to synthesise certain (I) and 6-piperidino/morpholinomethyl derivatives (II, III). The compounds (I, II, III) thus synthesised have been tested against *Schizopyrenus russelli* for their ability to cause excystment and for their cysticidal activity.

acetic acid or ethanol-acetic acid afforded I. Reaction of piperidine or morpholine with formalin and I under the conditions of Mannich reaction yielded II and III. *o*-Phenylenediamines required for the syntheses of I were either available commercially or were synthesised in the laboratory by a series of steps. 3,4-Diaminobenzoic acid has earlier been prepared⁸ by the coupling of diazotised sulfanilamide with 4-aminobenzoic acid followed by the reduction of the diazo-compound. We have prepared it by a different procedure outlined in Scheme A. 4-Chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine was also prepared by the same procedure. I, II and III thus synthesised gave satisfactory elemental analyses. Additional support for their structures was derived from their infrared and N. M. R. spectral data. For instance N.M.R. spectrum of compound No. 18 taken in CDCl₃ was in accord with the assigned structure. The signals due to methylene protons of the morpholine ring attached to nitrogen and oxygen were observed at 2.62-2.73 δ and 3.60-3.70 δ respectively. The signal for methylene protons between two nitrogen atoms was centered at 5.12. Absorption due to methyl group occurred at 2.50 δ . Aromatic protons appeared as a complex pattern between 7.22-8.30 δ integrating for 7 protons.

For the synthesis of these compounds, the starting material indole-2,3-dione(s) was prepared via Sandmeyer reaction⁸, condensation of indole-2,3-dione(s) with *o*-phenylenediamine(s) in glacial

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were charted on a Perkin-Elmer 137 G Spectro-

* Part XIX of the series : Potential Biologically Active Agents

photometer in KBr and N.M.R. spectrum was recorded in CDCl_3 at 100 MHz using TMS as an internal standard.

***p*-Acetaminobenzoic Acid**: A mixture of *p*-aminobenzoic acid (10 g), glacial acetic acid (15 ml) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice. The white product thus separated, was filtered, washed with cold water and finally recrystallised from ethanol. Yield, 90% m.p. 251-52° (Lit¹⁰ m.p. 250°).

3-Nitro-4-acetaminobenzoic Acid: *p*-Acetaminobenzoic acid (5 g) was gradually stirred into a paste, prepared by adding 6.7 g of finely pulverized potassium nitrate to 30 ml of conc. sulfuric acid and the whole was kept at -10° to 0° in a freezing mixture bath. After all the *p*-acetaminobenzoic acid had been added, the mixture was kept at 0° for an hour and the syrupy mass then poured slowly on cracked ice. After standing for a short time, the yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water and finally recrystallised from ethanol yield 80% m.p. 220° (Lit¹¹ m.p. 220-21°).

3-Nitro-4-aminobenzoic Acid: 3-Nitro-4-acetaminobenzoic acid (5 g) was dissolved in 50 ml of cold conc. sulfuric acid and the solution was heated on a water bath for 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and cautiously stirred into crushed ice. The yellow precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed well with cold water and finally recrystallised from ethanol. Yield, 75% m.p. 281-82° (Lit¹² m.p. 284°).

3,4-Diaminobenzoic Acid: A clear solution of 3-nitro-4-aminobenzoic acid (1.82 g) was prepared in ethanol and transferred to a 250 ml flask. After

addition of Raney nickel (1 g) hydrazine hydrate (3 ml, 99%) was added in portions and the whole was refluxed till the yellow colour of the solution disappeared. The disappearance of the yellow colour indicated that the reduction is complete. It was then filtered under suction while hot. The clear solution (filtrate) was then distilled to remove the excess of ethanol. The residue thus left was cooled, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Yield 65%, m.p. 210° (Lit¹³ m.p. 210°).

Indophenazines(I)

Method A: To a clear solution of isatin (1.47 g) in the minimum quantity of hot acetic acid, was added 3,4-diaminobenzoic acid (1.32 g) in portions with thorough shaking. After addition were completed, the product started to separate out as yellow fine crystals in the hot reaction mixture, to ensure completion of the reaction, the whole was boiled for 5 min, then cooled and the product thus separated was filtered and finally recrystallised from acetic acid, yield 70%, m.p. >285°.

Method B: A mixture of isatin (1.47 g) and *o*-phenylenediamine (1.08 g) in 20 ml of ethanol containing two drops of glacial acetic acid, was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the solid mass thus separated, was filtered, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and recrystallised from acetic acid, yield 70%, m.p. 285°. Its m.m.p. with the product obtained by method A did not show any depression.

A number of unsubstituted and substituted indophenazines(I) thus prepared, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I—INDOPHENAZINES(I)

Sl. N.	R	R'	R''	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	%N analyses	
							Calcd.	Found
1. ^a	H	H	H	85	285	C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₂	—	—
2. ^b	Me	H	H	80	258	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂	—	—
3. ^c	Cl	H	H	90	>285	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClN ₂	—	—
4. ^d	Br	H	H	90	>285	C ₁₄ H ₇ BrN ₂	—	—
5. ^e	H	Me	Me	95	>285	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂	—	—
6.	Me	Me	Me	90	>290	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂	16.08	15.95
7. ^f	Cl	Me	Me	85	>290	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂	—	—
8. ^g	Br	Me	Me	90	>287	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrN ₂	—	—
9.	H	H	CO ₂ H	70	>285	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂	15.96	15.46
10. ^h	H	H	Cl	75	>275	C ₁₄ H ₇ ClN ₂	—	—
11.	Cl	H	Cl	70	>280	C ₁₄ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₂	14.58	14.18
12.	Me	H	Cl	75	275-77	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₂	15.69	15.94

Lit.¹⁴ m.p. a, 285-87°; c, 300°; d, 279-80°; e, 352-53°

Lit.¹⁵ m.p. e, 352-58°; f, 370-71°; g, 360-61°.

b, h, used directly for the syntheses of II and III respectively.

I. R. data (μ):

Compound No. 9, C=O, 5.92, -NH or OH, 3.22.

TABLE 2—6-PIPERIDINOMETHYLINDOPHENAZINES(II) AND 6-MORPHOLINOMETHYL INDOPHENAZINES(III)

Sl. N.	R	R'	X	Yield %	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	%N analyses	
							Calcd.	Found
13.	H	H	OH ₂	65	127-28	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄	17.70	17.92
14.	Cl	H	OH ₂	75	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄	15.97	15.98
15.	Br	H	CH ₃	70	165	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ BrN ₄	14.17	13.57
16.	H	4-Cl	OH ₂	75	172-73	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ClN ₄	15.97	15.55
17.	H	H	O	65	133	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₄ O	17.59	16.93
18.	Me	H	O	60	156-57	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O	16.85	16.38
19.	Cl	H	O	70	182	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O	15.88	15.67
20.	Br	H	O	70	178	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ O	14.10	14.47

I. R. data (μ)

Compound No. 14, C=N, 6.33, CH₂, 3.42.

6-Piperidinomethylindophenazines(II) :

Indophenazine (0.01 mole) was suspended in 20 ml of warm ethanol containing two drops of dimethyl formamide. To this suspension there was added 2 ml of 37% formalin and 0.85 g (0.01 mole) of piperidine with vigorous stirring. The mixture was then heated on a water bath for 10 min. and thereafter allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The product thus separated was filtered, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and dried well in air. It was finally recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) yield 50%, m.p. 127-28°.

6-Morpholinomethylindophenazines(III) : A suspension of indophenazine (0.01 mole) in 20 ml of ethanol containing two drops of dimethyl formamide was warmed and to which 2 ml of 37% formalin and 0.87 g (0.01 mole) of morpholine was added with vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 10 min. to ensure the completion of the reaction and then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The solid thus deposited, was filtered, washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and dried well in air. The well dried product was then recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), yield 55%, m.p. 133°.

A number such products (II and III) were prepared and are shown in Table 2.

Attempts to crystallise II and III from ethanol resulted in the delinking of the Mannich group.

Biological Activity^{1,4} : None of these compounds showed any excystment activity or cysticidal action against *Schizopyrenus russelli*, but all were found to extend the period of the excystment of the cysts from 24 to 48 hr.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the Head of the Chemistry Department for providing facilities. Facilities and assistance provided by Dr. S. R. Das during biological screening is gratefully acknowledged. I. A. K. is grateful to I. C. M. R., New Delhi, for the award of a J. R. F. Elemental analyses and spectral data were obtained from C. D. R. I., Lucknow on payment basis.

References

1. T. S. OSDANE in Medicinal Chemistry, 3rd. Ed. A. BURGER, Editor (Wiley Interscience, New York, N. Y.) 1970, p. 662.
2. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, **64**, 881.
3. R. CAVIER, R. ROYER, R. RIPS and L. RENE, *Chim. Ther.*, 1969, **4**, 21; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **70**, 113686.
4. John Wyeth and Brothers Ltd., *Brit.* 1,240,648 (1971). *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 118342.
5. S. A. IMAM and R. S. VARMA, *Experientia*, 1975, **31**, 1287.
6. R. S. VARMA and I. A. KHAN, *Polish. J. Pharmacol. Pharm.*, 1977, **29**, 549.
7. R. S. VARMA and I. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1978, **67**, 315.
8. C. S. MARVEL and G. S. Hiers, *Org. Synth*, 1941, Col. Vol. 1, 321.
9. C. MUSANTE and L. FABBRINI, *Sperimentale, Sez. Chim. Biol.*, 1952, **3**, 33; *Chem. Abs.* 1953, **47**, 6889.
10. F. ULLMANN and J. B. UZBACHIAN, *Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1801.
11. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen Chemie, Verlag Von Julius Springer, Berlin, 1931, **14**, 444.
12. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen Chemie, Verlag Von Julius Springer, Berlin, 1931, **14**, 440.
13. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen Chemie, Verlag Von Julius Springer, Berlin, 1931, **14**, 451.
14. S. R. DAS, U. SAXENA and B. N. SINGH. *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1963, **23**, 57.
15. Beilsteins Handbuch Der Organischen Chemie, Verlag Von Julius Springer, Berlin, 1937, **26**, 88.
16. S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANNERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 264.